

1 **Low-Temperature Pyrometallurgical Recycling Pre-Treatment for Lithium-Ion**
2 **Batteries: Understanding of Thermal Decomposition and Surface Changes**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 Escalating global lithium-ion battery demand necessitates efficient end-of-life management.
18 Pyrometallurgical recycling offers a promising route for metal recovery and environmental
19 impact minimization. However, optimizing low-temperature pre-treatment for complete
20 organic removal while preserving active material integrity remains challenging. This study
21 investigated thermal decomposition and surface changes of key battery components (NMC622
22 cathode, graphite anode, polymeric separator) from 100 to 800 °C, focusing on the 400-650 °C
23 industrial interval. Material responses were characterized using TGA-MS, isothermal mass loss,
24 and SEM-EDS. A 500 °C treatment was identified as optimal, enabling complete organic
25 carbon removal within one hour without compromising NMC spinel structure or current

26 collector degradation. This precise control reduces energy consumption and mitigates
27 hazardous gas release, enhancing environmental sustainability. Findings define parameters for
28 efficient electroactive material separation, providing a practical, scalable, and cost-effective
29 strategy for improving battery recycling. This work advances low-temperature
30 pyrometallurgical processing understanding, supporting a circular economy for critical
31 materials.

32

33 **Keywords:** lithium-ion battery, recycling, pyrometallurgy, high-temperature treatment,
34 thermal decomposition, surface changes

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37 The escalating global demand for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), especially in electric
38 vehicles (EVs), necessitates efficient and sustainable end-of-life management strategies [1], [2].
39 In parallel, growing environmental concerns and the limited availability of critical raw materials
40 such as lithium, cobalt, and nickel underscore the importance of developing circular economy
41 solutions that support resource security and industrial resilience [3], [4].

42 Conventional pyrometallurgical recycling of LIBs typically involves a two-step process:
43 a low-temperature stage (up to ~ 800 °C) to decompose organics and separate cell components,
44 followed by high-temperature smelting (between 1500 and 1800 °C) for metal recovery [5], [6].
45 The first stage conditions the internal electrode–separator assembly and mitigates safety
46 hazards from residual electrolytes and flammable materials [7]. This step is often decoupled
47 from metallurgical recovery to control organic degradation better, preserve active materials’
48 integrity, and facilitate delamination for downstream recovery. However, decomposition
49 involves overlapping reactions with specific onset temperatures, requiring precise process
50 control. Among various chemistries, lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) is widely

51 studied due to its prevalence in high-energy cells and complex thermochemical behaviour [8].
52 Industrially, external casings (polymer-laminated aluminium or nickel) are removed before
53 thermal treatment, so research focuses on the internal stack: cathode, anode, and separator [7],
54 [9].

55 NMC cathodes are generally thermally stable relative to organic compounds, but their
56 behaviour depends on delithiation and residual binders or salts [10]. While the spinel structure
57 may persist up to 800 °C [11], side reactions involving lithium salts (e.g., lithium
58 hexafluorophosphate, LiPF_6 ; lithium fluoride, LiF ; lithium carbonate, Li_2CO_3) can lead to
59 the release of carbon dioxide (CO_2) or hydrogen fluoride (HF) and phosphorus-containing
60 gases [12], [13]. Furthermore, the aluminium (Al) current collector, with a melting point of
61 ~ 660 °C, may melt and encapsulate active material if temperatures exceed this threshold [14],
62 [15], compromising downstream separation and material quality [6], [16], [17]. Therefore,
63 precise temperature control is critical to remove organic compounds while preserving cathode
64 integrity [18].

65 Graphite anodes exhibit high thermal stability under inert atmospheres but oxidise in air
66 above ~ 500 °C, resulting in significant CO_2 release and mass loss [19]. Complete combustion
67 typically occurs between 600 and 700 °C, depending on oxygen content in the atmosphere,
68 heating rate, and surface area [19]–[21]. Residual surface compounds, such as lithium alkyl
69 carbonates or Li_2CO_3 , originating from solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer degradation,
70 may also affect the oxidation pathway and initiate earlier decomposition [22].

71 Polymeric separators, typically made of polyethylene (PE) or polypropylene (PP), begin
72 to degrade below 200 °C. This involves initial melting followed by decomposition into
73 hydrocarbon species [23]–[25]. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), commonly used as a binder,
74 decomposes between 350 and 500 °C, releasing HF , water, and low-molecular-weight
75 fragments [26]. Above 500 °C, remaining residues are mostly converted into stable inorganic

76 phases; for example, alumina-coated separators may yield aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) after
77 treatment [25].

78 Given the complexity of multi-component battery architectures, most studies on low-
79 temperature pyrometallurgical pre-treatment have focused on achieving efficient organic
80 removal while preserving valuable materials, as both are essential for scalable LIB
81 recycling [27]–[30]. Thermal exposure between 500 and 600 °C is widely regarded as a critical
82 step for decomposing polymeric binders and evaporating electrolyte residues, thereby
83 improving the efficiency of mechanical comminution and downstream metal recovery [29].
84 However, temperatures above 600 °C can lead to the embrittlement or melting of Al foils,
85 complicating their separation. In parallel, elevated temperatures also promote the carbothermic
86 reduction of active materials, such as LiCoO_2 , which begins decomposing around 700 °C and
87 affects both mass loss and lithium recovery yields. Although reviews of pre-treatment strategies
88 confirm that calcination between 150 and 650 °C efficiently removes conductive carbon and
89 organic compounds, reducing binder adhesion and enhancing separability, they also emphasise
90 challenges related to high energy demands and the release of hazardous gases, including toxic
91 fluorinated species [27], [29]. Despite these advances, a detailed, component-specific
92 understanding of thermal degradation, particularly how controlled heating influences the
93 structure, surface chemistry, and separability of individual active materials and polymeric
94 separators, remains limited. Such insights are crucial for the development of energy-efficient,
95 scalable recycling processes that not only ensure effective organic removal but also minimise
96 unwanted side reactions and preserve material functionality [30], [31].

97 Thus, this work systematically investigates the thermal degradation and surface
98 evolution of the NMC622 cathode, graphite anode, and polymeric separator across a broad
99 temperature range of 100 to 800 °C, particularly emphasizing the 400 to 650 °C interval
100 commonly utilised in industrial pre-treatment. Detailed insights into material responses were

101 provided by employing dynamic thermogravimetric analysis coupled with mass
102 spectrometry (TGA-MS), isothermal mass loss evaluation, and high-resolution scanning
103 electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The results
104 indicated treatment at 500 °C to allow complete removal of organic constituents within one
105 hour, critically preserving the structural and functional integrity of electrochemically active
106 materials and current collectors. This identified optimal temperature offers a crucial balance
107 between efficiency and material preservation, thereby providing practical guidance for
108 designing energy-efficient and scalable recycling processes that support the broader
109 implementation of circular economy principles for critical raw materials.

110

111 **2. Materials and Methods**

112 **2.1 Material**

113 The LIB pouch cells used in this study possess a nominal voltage of 3.65 V and a rated
114 capacity of 78 Ah. These cells were previously characterised in our previous work by
115 Pražanová et al. [32]. Each cell comprises 36 stacked layers comprising NMC622 cathode
116 materials, where the numbers indicate the molar ratio of Ni:Mn:Co, a polymer separator, and
117 graphite-based anode layers. The electrolyte consists of LiPF₆ in an organic solvent, and the
118 entire assembly is encapsulated in a flexible polymer–aluminium laminated pouch.

119 Initially used in a fully electric vehicle, the battery module had a nominal voltage
120 of 29.36 V and a total energy capacity of 6.85 kWh. Before disassembly, the module was deeply
121 discharged (voltage level approximately 0 V). The module's casing was carefully milled open
122 to access the internal cells, and the adhesive bonding was weakened by applying alcohol to
123 facilitate their separation. Subsequently, the cells were manually extracted from the opened
124 module. The open structure of the module, individual battery cells, procedure of their opening,
125 and specimen preparation and characterisation are shown in Figure 1.

127

128 Figure 1: Overview of the experimental workflow: opening of the battery module, extraction
 129 and disassembly of pouch cells, preparation of specimens of battery materials, and subsequent
 130 morphological and elemental analyses (scanning electron microscopy, SEM; energy-dispersive
 131 X-ray spectroscopy, EDS) followed by thermal analyses (thermogravimetric analysis, TGA;
 132 thermogravimetric analysis coupled with mass spectrometry, TGA-MS).

133

134 2.2 Methods

135 2.2.1 Specimen Preparation

136 A set of samples was prepared for analysis to monitor changes in morphology and
 137 surface composition induced by thermal treatment. The battery cell was carefully disassembled
 138 using a ceramic knife, and individual components, specifically the cathode enclosed within

139 the separator pouch and the anode, were isolated. All procedures were conducted inside
140 a laboratory fume hood.

141 Following disassembly, as described in Figure 1, intact electrodes and the separator
142 layers were pre-dried at ambient temperature to evaporate the carbonates. The pre-dried layers
143 were subsequently sectioned into 25×25 mm square samples using a precision paper cutter.
144 Afterwards, the sections were dried at 60°C until no further decreases in mass were observed
145 (approximately one week). The final samples were weighed in porcelain crucibles using an
146 analytical balance.

147 The specimens were classified into three groups according to their functional role within
148 the cell: cathode, anode, and separator. In addition, a fourth reference group was prepared,
149 consisting of the cathode layer covered by a separator on both sides, to control potential
150 interfacial effects. This configuration deviates from the standard architecture, in which
151 separators on both sides typically enclose the cathode. Five independent replicates were
152 measured for each sample category to ensure statistical validity.

153 For the thermal degradation analyses, circular samples with a diameter of 5 mm were
154 punched from an unopened battery cell using a manual puncher. These specimens comprised
155 the entire cross-section of the battery cell, including spinel, separator, and graphite layers, and
156 are hereinafter referred to as “cross-section samples.” In addition to the full cross-section
157 samples, a separate specimen of cathode, anode, and the cathode with a two-sided separator
158 was explicitly prepared for TGA-MS measurements.

159

160 *2.2.2 Material Characterisation Methods*

161 *Thermogravimetric Analysis*

162 Thermal degradation in dynamic mode was assessed using a thermogravimetric analyser
163 (Discovery TGA550 Auto Advanced, TA Instruments, USA). A cross-section specimen,

164 including all electrochemically active layers with a weight of approximately 25 mg, was
165 subjected to heating from room temperature (24 °C) to 1000 °C at a constant heating rate
166 of 10 °C·min⁻¹ in an air atmosphere with a flow rate of 65 mL·min⁻¹.

167

168 *Thermogravimetric Analysis – Mass Spectrometry*

169 The chemical composition of degradation products was investigated using coupled
170 TGA-MS. The following sample types were analysed: cross-section, anode, cathode, and
171 cathode with one-sided separator. Measurements were performed on a TG-DTA Setsys
172 Evolution system (Setaram, France) coupled to an OmniStarTM quadrupole mass spectrometer
173 (Pfeiffer Vacuum, Germany).

174 Before thermal treatment, all samples were stabilised at 30 °C for 30 minutes.
175 Subsequently, the samples were heated in an air atmosphere at a constant heating rate
176 of 10 °C·min⁻¹. After the heating and thermogravimetric data acquisition were completed, the
177 samples were allowed to cool under ambient conditions, while mass spectrometric data
178 acquisition continued for an additional 50 minutes. Mass spectra were recorded up to 150 m/z
179 (mass-to-charge ratio) with a resolution of 1 m/z; each spectrum was acquired over 8 seconds,
180 corresponding to a dwell time of 53 milliseconds per m/z unit. The data obtained from TGA
181 and MS were synchronously aligned, processed, annotated, and visualised using OriginPro
182 software. Representative ions corresponding to specific compounds or chemical groups were
183 selected based on the NIST17 library of electron ionisation spectra.

184

185 *Static Thermal Mass Loss Analysis*

186 Samples were placed in a CLASIC laboratory furnace with a front-opening design for
187 static thermogravimetric measurements. Heating was performed at 5 °C·min⁻¹ to target
188 temperatures of 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, and 800 °C, each followed by a one-hour

189 isothermal hold, then cooled to room temperature by natural convection overnight. The
190 relatively high heating rate and short exposure time were chosen to reduce the required time to
191 effectively obtain the studied materials, which corresponds to the study's objectives and the
192 economic demands of industrial use. This approach is relevant for pyrometallurgical
193 pretreatment in battery recycling, where energy efficiency and time optimisation are critical.
194 Temperatures were selected to identify the minimum effective recycling threshold under
195 economic constraints, focusing in detail on the 400 to 650 °C range, with measurements at 400,
196 450, 500, 550, 600, and 650 °C.

197 After cooling to ambient temperature under natural conditions, gravimetric
198 measurements were performed using a calibrated KERN analytical balance to evaluate mass
199 loss resulting from thermal exposure. Each sample type was measured in five independent
200 replicates, and the mass was recorded to four decimal places to ensure high precision.
201 This methodology enabled a comprehensive assessment of thermally induced mass changes,
202 enhancing understanding of material decomposition behaviour across various temperature
203 conditions.

204

205 *Scanning Electron Microscopy*

206 Following thermal exposure, the samples were subjected to structural and compositional
207 analyses to assess changes induced by heat treatment. SEM was employed to examine
208 modifications in surface morphology using a TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU scanning electron
209 microscope. Imaging was conducted at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV, a working distance of
210 15 mm, and a beam intensity of 15 nA, utilising both secondary and backscattered electrons at
211 a magnification of 2000×.

212 To complement the morphological investigation, EDS was performed to determine
213 alterations in elemental composition. Measurements were conducted using an OXFORD

214 Instruments INCA 350 EDS analyser, enabling precise chemical microanalysis of the observed
215 samples. Data were processed using AZtec software (version 4.4), with composition
216 measurements taken over an area of 0.005 mm², yielding an accuracy of ±0.1 % for each
217 measured point. Micro-X-ray elemental mapping was also carried out to visualise the spatial
218 distribution of elements across the sample surface.

219

220 **3. Results and Discussion**

221 *3.1 Dynamic Thermal Degradation Analysis*

222 The thermal degradation of the cross-section sample in an air atmosphere is a complex
223 process involving multiple decomposition steps. While residual weight at a given temperature
224 is observable, a static thermal weight loss test on a larger scale was also performed due to the
225 dynamic nature of the measurement and the small sample size. The distinct decomposition steps
226 are visible in the temperature weight derivative curve shown in Figure 2a. The first significant
227 weight loss, characterised by a peak around 120 °C, is followed by a double peak with maxima
228 around 250 °C and 350 °C. A further small weight loss peak was observed around 450 °C.
229 The most intensive weight loss occurred between 550 and 750 °C. High-temperature weight
230 loss (above 900 °C) was also observed, which might be connected to fluorine release,
231 as described in work by Ross et al. [33].

232

233 Figure 2: Thermal degradation analysis of the cross-section sample: a) TGA profile showing
 234 sample weight loss (blue) and its temperature derivative (green). b) Coupled TGA-MS analysis
 235 presenting the same thermal profile and mass spectrometric signals for selected degradation
 236 products.

237 While TGA provides valuable insight into the thermal degradation behaviour of
 238 materials, it is insufficient to identify decomposition products. Therefore, TGA-MS was used
 239 to detect and identify evolved gases. The results in Figure 2b include the TGA temperature
 240 profile, followed by the weight loss curve and its first derivative in the second row.

241 The subsequent rows display MS signal intensities for selected mass-to-charge (m/z) ratios: 15,
242 18, 20, 29, and 44, chosen for their relevance to degradation pathways and evolved moieties.
243 Ion 15 corresponds to the methyl moiety, 18 to water, 20 to HF (though it may also arise from
244 water containing the ^{18}O isotope), 29 to ethyl, formyl, or carbon monoxide, and 44 to CO_2 .
245 Water, HF, and CO_2 were selected as indicative degradation products of the PVDF binder [33],
246 [34]. HF also originates from the thermal breakdown of the LiPF_6 electrolyte. Methyl and ethyl
247 groups are typically associated with carbonate-based electrolyte solvents or with the thermal
248 degradation of the PE separator. Additionally, CO_2 is a known oxidative degradation product
249 of graphite. However, due to the mass spectrometric resolution of 1 m/z unit, co-eluting or
250 overlapping signals from other fragments cannot be excluded. For the same reason, CO was
251 omitted from interpretation as its nominal mass is the same as N_2 in the carrier gas.

252 Decomposition of the cross-section sample is first indicated by the emergence of peaks
253 for methyl and ethyl groups around $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, associated with the evaporation of carbonate-based
254 solvents, most likely dimethyl or diethyl carbonate and methyl ethyl carbonate. A broad signal
255 range for methyl, water, hydrogen fluoride, and ethyl between 225 and $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ reflects the
256 decomposition of lithium alkyl carbonates [35]. The water signal appears as a doublet, with
257 a second local maximum at approximately $375\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to the thermal degradation of
258 the PE separator. This is accompanied by ion 15, indicating CH_3 moieties released during the
259 cleavage of PE chains. Water peak tails extending up to $530\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are likely attributed to the
260 decomposition of the PVDF binder. At temperatures exceeding $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a broad CO_2 signal is
261 observed, corresponding to the thermo-oxidative degradation of the graphite anode.

262 Similar TGA–MS measurements were performed on individual anode, cathode, and
263 cathode-with-separator samples. The obtained profiles exhibited comparable trends with
264 sample-specific variations; the cross-section sample profile (see Figure 2b), however, provides
265 a representative overview and serves as the primary reference for interpretation.

266 The anode sample exhibited broad peaks of water, hydrogen fluoride, methyl, and ethyl
267 groups centred around 350 °C, primarily from decomposing lithium alkyl carbonates [35].
268 The tailing of water and hydrogen fluoride signals, absent for methyl and ethyl ions, is likely
269 associated with the degradation of the PVDF polymeric binder, similarly to what was observed
270 for the cross-section sample. The release of carbon dioxide, attributed to the thermo-oxidative
271 degradation of graphite, began around 500 °C. As pristine graphite is known for its high thermal
272 stability, the observed shift suggests that degradation during battery operation may reduce this
273 stability.

274 The cathode and cathode-with-separator samples displayed behaviour with notable
275 differences from the cross-section and anode specimens. In the cathode-with-separator sample,
276 the signals for methyl and ethyl groups appeared as distinct doublets, with lower-temperature
277 peaks (around 200 °C) attributed to PE degradation. These peaks were less prominent in the
278 cross-section data, likely due to their relatively low intensity and overlap with the end of
279 carbonates evaporation. For the same sample, the water and carbon dioxide intensities peaked
280 around 375 °C and were noticeably elevated, suggesting ongoing degradation of the PE
281 separator. Both cathode-based measurements exhibited broad carbon dioxide peaks around
282 325 °C and 550 °C, even without graphite. These observations indicate that complex reactions
283 may occur within the cathode layers [36]. Avoiding cathode exposure to temperatures above
284 500 °C is recommended to minimise these undesirable decomposition processes.

285

286 *3.2 Static Thermal Mass Loss Analysis*

287 Understanding individual LIB components' thermal decomposition behaviour and
288 residual mass is crucial for designing efficient and safe recycling processes. Therefore, their
289 thermal degradation patterns were assessed by monitoring mass loss after controlled heating
290 steps. Figure 3 illustrates the components' comprehensive mass loss profiles across a broad

291 temperature range (0–800 °C). An initial minor mass loss, observed in all samples below
292 100 °C, is primarily attributed to the evaporation of residual electrolyte. Following this,
293 significant thermal degradation of organic components commences in the separator,
294 predominantly evidenced by mass loss between 100 and 300 °C. This temperature window
295 represents the primary thermal degradation of the separator's polymer matrix. By approximately
296 500 °C, these organic constituents were almost entirely decomposed, although minor residues
297 of decomposition products persisted, as confirmed in studies by Mouse et al. [37] and Sadeghi
298 and Restuccia [38].

299 The anode exhibits minimal mass loss up to approximately 500 °C, after which a sharp
300 and substantial mass loss is observed, indicative of the decomposition of its organic binders and
301 residual carbonaceous materials. Conversely, the cathode and the cathode with separator
302 demonstrate high intrinsic thermal stability, with low mass loss recorded across the 100–800 °C
303 range.

304 Quantitative analysis of these mass loss profiles provides critical insights into optimal
305 thermal pre-treatment strategies for LIB recycling. The pronounced mass loss events observed
306 at specific temperatures correlate strongly with underlying decomposition processes within the
307 battery components. A temperature of approximately 500 °C was identified as an optimal upper
308 limit for preserving material integrity and enabling efficient mechanical separation; this
309 temperature balance is crucial for energy-efficient processing and reducing potential hazardous
310 emissions. At this point, the separator is transformed mainly into refractory Al₂O₃, which may
311 facilitate targeted surface functionalisation, and enhances the efficiency of downstream metal
312 recovery by minimizing impurities [25], [32].

313

314 Figure 3: Static thermal mass loss analysis of lithium-ion battery cell components (cathode,
 315 anode, separator, and cathode with separator) from 0–800 °C, illustrating their distinct thermal
 316 stabilities and highlighting key decomposition and processing temperature ranges with standard
 317 deviation error bars. Note that data points for the cathode with separator sample at 450, 550,
 318 and 650 °C are linearly interpolated for visual trend continuity.

319

To further characterise the precise thermal behaviour of key components within the most
 320 critical range for pyrometallurgical pre-treatment [37], [39], mass loss observations were
 321 focused within the 400 to 650 °C temperature range. This window specifically captures the
 322 onset and progression of significant mass loss from the anode and the final stages of separator
 323 degradation, which are crucial for defining optimal pre-treatment conditions. It is important to
 324 note that for the 'Cathode with separator' sample, data points at 450, 550, and 650 °C were not
 325 experimentally determined, and its trend line in Figure 3 is linearly interpolated for visual
 326 continuity. Conversely, exposure to higher temperatures between 600 and 800 °C led to
 327 oxidation and structural degradation of metallic components, particularly the Al current

328 collector in NMC cathodes. This degradation was found to reduce material recovery efficiency
329 and compromise the quality of recovered fractions.

330

331 *3.3 Morphological and Elemental Composition Changes Analysis*

332 Building upon the insights from thermal mass loss analysis, further investigation was
333 conducted into the structural and compositional stability of the cathode materials. In line with
334 the recycling objectives that prioritise the recovery of valuable metals found primarily in battery
335 cathodes [30], [40], thermally exposed cathode samples were analysed to examine their
336 morphological and structural changes using SEM and EDS. Figure 4 illustrates the
337 representative initial condition of the dried cathode before thermal treatment, along with
338 elemental maps depicting both the baseline state and the state after exposure to the highest
339 temperature achieved (800 °C). This approach was employed to evaluate the surface
340 composition of the cathode and to track the compositional changes resulting from heat treatment
341 across a temperature range of 100 to 800 °C, with increments of 100 °C. The comprehensive
342 results for all exposed cathode samples are provided in Figure 5.

343

344 Figure 4: Illustration of (a) SEM measurements for the untreated cathode sample using
345 secondary electrons imaging - left, backscattered electrons imaging - right; (b) EDS mapping
346 for the untreated cathode sample (T0) compared to the thermally treated cathode sample at
347 800 °C (T800). 'T' denotes the specific temperature at which the analysis was performed.

348 The findings indicate that the investigated NMC layer possesses exceptional thermal
349 stability, such that exposure to temperatures of 800 °C does not significantly alter the properties
350 of this crystalline spinel structure. However, a critical observation was the onset of melting of
351 the Al current collector at 700 °C. This melting event significantly compromises the integrity
352 of the surrounding electroactive material by causing delamination and potential encapsulation,
353 thereby diminishing the quality of the recovered NMC spinel and increasing the complexity for
354 subsequent purification. The ultimate objective of the thermal treatment process is to achieve a
355 temperature regime that maintains the original properties of the valuable electroactive materials
356 while effectively removing all organic components and facilitating their subsequent separation
357 from current collectors, supporting high-value material recovery.

358

359 Figure 5: Illustration of (a) SEM measurements for the cathode sample across a temperature
 360 range of 100-800 °C, with increments of 100 °C, using secondary electrons imaging - left,

361 backscattered electrons imaging - right. 'T' denotes the specific temperature at which the
362 analysis was performed.

363

364 Complementing the morphological observations, detailed elemental analysis of the
365 thermally treated cathode surfaces was performed using EDS. The study primarily focused on
366 key electroactive elements (Ni, Mn, Co) and tracking changes in carbon and fluorine residues,
367 as presented in Figure 6. Beyond these primary targets, various other elements were identified,
368 indicative of residues originating from auxiliary battery materials, including Al (from Al₂O₃,
369 a separator residue [25]), P (from the decomposition of LiPF₆ [12], [13]), W (traces of WO₃,
370 a stabiliser in NMC spinel [41], [42]), and O (common to all oxide species [43]). Their
371 identification provided insights into potential contamination sources and the completeness of
372 organic removal following thermal treatment. It's important to note that metallic Al and Cu
373 from current collectors cannot be evaluated by surface analysis of electrodes using EDS.

374

375 Figure 6: EDS analysis of cathode surface composition after thermal exposure at selected
 376 temperatures: (a) full range from 0 to 800 °C in 100 °C increments; (b) detailed range from 400
 377 to 650 °C in 50 °C increments. ‘T’ indicates the specific temperature at which each sample was
 378 analysed.

379 A critical compositional shift was observed at approximately 400 °C, manifesting as
 380 a substantial reduction in organic carbon and fluorine content. These changes led to a relative
 381 increase in NMC metal content (Ni, Mn, Co) due to the elimination of organic components, as
 382 evident from the graphs showing a significant increase in the relative yield of target elements

383 from 400 °C. Notably, at 500 °C, the carbon signal was absent, confirming complete removal
384 of the organic matrix without observable degradation of the NMC phase. Further investigation
385 into narrower temperature intervals revealed that residual carbon was fully combusted even at
386 450 °C with one hour of exposure. However, complete fluorine removal was only achieved at
387 higher temperatures, approximately 700 °C, indicating the presence of more thermally stable
388 fluorine-containing compounds at 500 °C. The persistence of these fluorides at 500 °C
389 is a critical consideration, as they can complicate subsequent hydrometallurgical leaching and
390 may contribute to equipment corrosion or lower final product purity. Regarding other elements,
391 residual P from the electrolyte remained unchanged, while oxygen showed an opposite trend,
392 growing at the highest temperatures due to high-temperature oxidation. Among the identified
393 contaminants, only refractory Al₂O₃ and WO₃ persisted throughout the entire heat treatment.
394 Despite the incomplete fluorine removal at 500 °C, this temperature was reaffirmed as optimal
395 for pyrometallurgical pre-treatment, as it effectively combines extensive organic purification
396 (especially carbon removal) with excellent preservation of the electroactive material structure
397 before significant current collector degradation.

398 The systematic analysis of electrode materials subjected to high-temperature exposure
399 for one hour across a range of temperatures from 100 to 800 °C, explicitly focusing on NMC
400 cathodes, graphite anodes, and polymeric separators, has yielded valuable insights into their
401 thermal behaviour. The most significant changes in mass and composition were consistently
402 observed between 400 and 650 °C. This comprehensive investigation underscores the suitability
403 of high-temperature pyrometallurgical approaches for recovering and recycling electroactive
404 materials from spent batteries.

405 At 100 °C, electrode materials undergo thorough drying to a constant mass. Subsequent
406 heating to 200 °C initiates the oxidation and browning of PE within the separator, alongside the
407 decomposition of PVDF binder. At 300 °C, the oxidation of the separator polymer progresses,

408 accompanied by the liberation of fluorine compounds. The first significant changes in relative
409 composition are observed at 400 °C, primarily marked by the onset of carbon combustion. By
410 500 °C, all organic carbon is eliminated; however, this temperature also initiates the oxidation
411 of the anodic graphite. The most pronounced oxidation of graphite on the anode occurs at
412 600 °C, while cathodic layers remain stable. Concurrently, the separator polymer decreases in
413 mass linearly with increasing temperature, and the electroactive material detaches slightly from
414 the current collector. At 700 °C, almost all graphite on the anode is oxidised, but importantly,
415 the Al current collector on the cathode begins to melt, potentially reducing the quality of the
416 NMC spinel. Even at 800 °C, where the copper current collector of the anode oxidises and
417 samples disintegrate into powder, it was demonstrated that the NMC spinel crystals largely
418 retain their characteristic structure.

419 Based on these findings, a temperature of 500 °C has been identified as optimal for the
420 pyrometallurgical separation of electroactive electrode materials. This temperature effectively
421 removes the binder and facilitates straightforward separation of electroactive materials from
422 their current collectors, which remain largely undegraded after just one hour of exposure.
423 At lower temperatures, the persistence of organic compounds from the electrolyte and binder
424 polymers significantly impedes the separation of electroactive materials and the polymeric
425 separator. Conversely, higher temperatures lead to detrimental oxidative degradation of anodic
426 graphite and metallic current collectors (Al and Cu). While the NMC spinel from the cathode
427 surface remains stable up to 800 °C, its purity and thus the efficiency of separation are
428 compromised at elevated temperatures. Although graphite oxidation at higher temperatures
429 could potentially be mitigated by heat treatment in a specialised furnace under an inert
430 atmosphere, such a process would substantially increase the cost of product recovery, and
431 residuum from organic carbon compounds might persist. Furthermore, Al, P, and W
432 contaminating compounds from the original product persist in the recovered electroactive

433 materials after heat treatment, suggesting a potential need for subsequent hydrometallurgical
434 purification to achieve a high-purity final product.

435 **5. Conclusion**

436 The thermal behaviour of key LIB components (NMC cathodes, graphite anodes, and
437 polymeric separators) was systematically examined across a comprehensive temperature range
438 of 100 to 800 °C, with a specific focus on the industrially relevant window of 400 to 650 °C.
439 Unlike prior fragmented studies, an integrated experimental approach was utilised, revealing
440 critical inter-component interactions and their impact on material integrity during low-
441 temperature pyrometallurgical pre-treatment. The results show that a treatment temperature of
442 500 °C offers the best balance for pyrometallurgical pre-treatment, allowing complete removal
443 of organic binders and electrolyte residues within one hour. At this temperature, electroactive
444 materials can be effectively separated from current collectors, which remain mostly intact.
445 Lower temperatures did not eliminate organic carbon compounds, complicating separation,
446 while higher temperatures led to oxidation of graphite and mechanical degradation of collectors.
447 Despite the thermal stability of NMC cathodes up to 800 °C, their purity decreases at higher
448 temperatures due to interactions with molten current collectors. The findings confirm that
449 treatment within this specific temperature range is favourable for preserving active materials
450 while enabling efficient removal of organics, thereby providing practical insight for the
451 development of energy-efficient, sustainable, and cost-effective LIB recycling processes.

452 This study, therefore, contributes to the basis of the design of thermally driven pre-
453 treatment strategies for EOL LIBs. By clearly defining 500 °C as a suitable operational
454 parameter, the work supports the development of energy-efficient, scalable processes that
455 minimize collector degradation and preserve the electrochemical integrity of active materials.
456 The retention of the NMC spinel structure at this temperature not only facilitates the recovery
457 of high-purity cathode material but also opens possibilities for direct re-use or simplified

458 downstream refining. These findings advance the understanding of low-temperature
459 pyrometallurgical processing and offer practical guidance for its implementation in industrial
460 recycling frameworks. As such, this approach supports the broader shift toward circular
461 economy practices in the field of critical raw materials management.

462

463 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

464 **Anna Pražanová:** Resources, Methodology, Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft,
465 Project administration.

466 **Jan Kočí:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualisation, Investigation, Writing – Original
467 draft, Writing – Review & Editing.

468 **Jonáš Uříčář:** Data curation, Investigation, Visualisation, Writing – Review & Editing

469 **Dominik Pilnaj:** Data curation, Investigation.

470 **Daniel-Ioan Stroe:** Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing.

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472 administration.

473

474 **Declaration of competing interest**

475 All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

476

477 **Data availability**

478 Data will be made available on request.

479

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487 **References**

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